

Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Ideals in Subtraction Algebra

Ramya M^{1,*}, Murali S², Radha R^{3,*}, Princy R⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Jansons Institute of Technology, Karumathampatti.; sramya.santhosh@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Coimbatore Institute of Technology, Coimbatore;
murali.s@cit.edu.in

³Professor, Department of Science and Humanities, RVS Technical Campus- Coimbatore;
radharmat2020@gmail.com

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Science and Humanities, Rathinam Technical Campus, Coimbatore;
princy.pjs@gmail.com

*Correspondence: sramya.santhosh@gmail.com, radharmat2020@gmail.com

Abstract. In this paper, the notions of a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Fuzzy subalgebra and a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Fuzzy ideal of a subtraction algebra are introduced and its characterizations of above are investigated.

Keywords: Subtraction algebra (Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic), subalgebra (Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic) ideal.

1. Introduction

The system of the form $(\phi; \circ,)$ was studied by B. M. Schein[7], where ϕ is a set of functions closed under the composition "o" of functions (so $(\phi; \circ)$ is a semigroup of functions) and the set theoretic subtraction "̸" (so $(\phi;)$ is a subtraction algebra). B. Zelinka[10] addressed a problem pertaining to the structure of multiplication in a subtraction semigroup that was put forth by B. M. Schein. For subtraction algebras of a particular kind known as the atomic subtraction algebras, he found a solution to the problem. The concept of ideals in subtraction algebras and their characterization were presented by Y. B. Jun et al[4,5]. The concepts of an intersectional soft subalgebra and an intersectional soft ideal of a subtraction algebra were presented by S. S. Ahn and Y. H. Kim[1], who also looked into some of their connected characteristics.

In 1965, Zadeh[9] defined the fuzzy set and introduced the degree of membership/truth (t). In 1986, Atanassov[2] defined the intuitionistic fuzzy set and introduced the degree of non-membership/falsehood (f) as a generalization of fuzzy sets. In 1995 (published in 1998), Smarandache[8] defined the Neutrosophic set on three components (t, i, f) = (truth, indeterminacy, falsity) and introduced the degree of indeterminacy/neutrality (i) as an independent component. M. Ramya[6] outlined a brand new mathematical approach of Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Sets (FQNS) in 2022.

In this paper, we introduce the notions of a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Fuzzy subalgebra and a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic of a subtraction algebra. Characterizations of Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra and a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic fuzzy ideal are investigated.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [3] An algebra $(X; -)$ is called a subtraction algebra if a single binary operation $-$ satisfies the following identities: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

$$x - (y - x) = x$$

$$x - (x - y) = y - (y - x)$$

$(x - y) - z = (x - z) - y$ We introduced an order relation X on a subtraction algebras:

$a \leq b \iff a - b = 0$ where $0 = a - a$ is an element that does not depend on the choice of $a \in X$.

Definition 2.2. [3] A neutrosophic set A of X is called a neutrosophic ideal of X if the following conditions are true $\forall x, y \in X$

$$N_A(x - y) \geq N_A(x) \text{ i.e., } t_A(x - y) \geq t_A(x); i_A(x - y) \geq i_A(x) \text{ and } f_A(x - y) \leq f_A(x);$$

$\exists x \vee y \Rightarrow N_A(x \vee y) \geq N_A(x) \wedge N_A(y)$ i.e., $t_A(x \vee y) \geq t_A(x) \wedge t_A(y); i_A(x \vee y) \geq i_A(x) \wedge i_A(y)$ and $f_A(x \vee y) \leq f_A(x) \vee f_A(y)$ whenever there exists $x \vee y$.

Definition 2.3. [6] Let X be a universe. A Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Set(FQN) $\hat{\mathbb{L}}$ on X is an object of the form

$$\hat{\mathbb{L}} = \{ \langle (x, \hat{\lambda}_{T_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}, \hat{\lambda}_{C_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}, \hat{\lambda}_{U_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}, \hat{\lambda}_{F_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}) : x \in X \rangle \}.$$

$$(\hat{\lambda}_{T_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}})^3 + (\hat{\lambda}_{C_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}})^3 + (\hat{\lambda}_{U_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}})^3 + (\hat{\lambda}_{F_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}})^3 \leq 2$$

Here $\hat{\lambda}_{T_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}(x)$ is the truth membership,

$\hat{\lambda}_{C_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}(x)$ is the contradiction membership,

$\hat{\lambda}_{U_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}(x)$ is the ignorance membership,

$\hat{\lambda}_{F_{\hat{\mathbb{L}}}}(x)$ is the falsity membership.

3. FQN Ideals in Subtraction Algebra

Definition 3.1.

A Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A in R is called a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R if it satisfies:

$$(5.1)(\forall x, y \in R)(TR_A(x-y) \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\}, CR_A(x-y) \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\}, UR_A(x-y) \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\} \text{ and } FR_A(x-y) \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\}).$$

Proposition 3.2.

Every Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R satisfies the following conditions:

$$(5.2)(\forall x \in R)(TR_A(0) \geq TR_A(x), CR_A(0) \geq CR_A(x), UR_A(0) \leq UR_A(x) \text{ and } FR_A(0) \leq FR_A(x)).$$

Example 3.3.

Let X = {0,1,2,3} be a subtraction algebra with the following table:

-	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Define a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A in R as follows:

$$TR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.83 & \text{if } x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \end{cases},$$

$$CR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.83 & \text{if } x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \end{cases},$$

$$UR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.11 & \text{if } x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.81 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \end{cases},$$

and

$$FR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.11 & \text{if } x \in \{0,3\} \\ 0.81 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \end{cases},$$

It is easy to check that A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R.

Theorem 3.4.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set in R and let $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \delta^2 + \xi^2 \leq 3$. Then A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R if and only if all of $(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)$ -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ are subalgebras of R when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)} \neq \emptyset$.

Proof.

Assume that A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R . Let $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi \in [0, 1]$ be such that $0 \leq \alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \delta^2 + \xi^2 \leq 3$ and $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)} \neq \emptyset$. Let $x, y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$. Then $TR_A(x) \geq \alpha, TR_A(y) \geq \alpha, CR_A(x) \geq \beta, CR_A(y) \geq \beta, UR_A(x) \leq \delta, UR_A(y) \leq \delta$ and $FR_A(x) \leq \xi, FR_A(y) \leq \xi$. Using (5.1), we have $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\} \geq \alpha$, $CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\} \geq \beta$, $UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\} \leq \delta$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\} \leq \xi$. Hence $x - y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$. Therefore $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ is a subalgebra of R .

Conversely, all of $(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)$ -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ are subalgebras of R when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)} \neq \emptyset$. Assume that there exist $a_t, b_t, a_i, b_i \in R$ and $a_f, b_f \in R$ such that $TR_A(a_t - b_t) < \min\{TR_A(a_t), TR_A(b_t)\}$, $CR_A(a_i - b_i) < \min\{CR_A(a_i), CR_A(b_i)\}$, $UR_A(a_f - b_f) > \max\{UR_A(a_f), UR_A(b_f)\}$ and $FR_A(a_f - b_f) > \max\{FR_A(a_f), FR_A(b_f)\}$. Then $TR_A(a_t - b_t) < \alpha_1 \leq \min\{TR_A(a_t), TR_A(b_t)\}$, $CR_A(a_i - b_i) < \beta_1 \leq \min\{CR_A(a_i), CR_A(b_i)\}$, $UR_A(a_f - b_f) > \delta_1 \geq \max\{UR_A(a_f), UR_A(b_f)\}$, and $FR_A(a_f - b_f) > \xi_1 \geq \max\{FR_A(a_f), FR_A(b_f)\}$ for some $\alpha_1, \beta_1 \in (0, 1]$ and $\delta_1, \xi_1 \in [0, 1)$. Hence $a_t, b_t, a_i, b_i \in A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \delta_1, \xi_1)}$, and $a_f, b_f \in A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \delta_1, \xi_1)}$. But $a_t - b_t, a_i - b_i \notin A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \delta_1, \xi_1)}$ and $a_f - b_f \notin A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \delta_1, \xi_1)}$, which is a contradiction. Hence $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\}$, $CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\}$, $UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\}$, $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\}$, for any $x, y, z \in R$. Therefore A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R .

Since $[0, 1]$ is a completely distributive lattice with respect to the usual ordering, we have the following theorem. \square

Theorem 3.5.

If $\{A_i | i \in N\}$ is a family of Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R , then $(\{A_i | i \in N\}, \subseteq)$ forms a complete distributive lattice.

Theorem 3.6.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R . If there exists a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in R such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} TR_A(a_n) = 1$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} CR_A(a_n) = 1$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} UR_A(a_n) = 0$, and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} FR_A(a_n) = 0$, then $TR_A(0) = 1$, $CR_A(0) = 1$, $UR_A(0) = 0$ and $FR_A(0) = 0$.

Proof.

By Proposition 5.3.2, we have $TR_A(0) \geq TR_A(x)$, $CR_A(0) \geq CR_A(x)$, $UR_A(0) \leq UR_A(x)$ and $FR_A(0) \leq FR_A(x)$ for all $x \in R$. Hence we have $TR_A(0) \geq TR_A(a_n)$, $CR_A(0) \geq CR_A(a_n)$, $UR_A(0) \leq UR_A(a_n)$ and $FR_A(0) \leq FR_A(a_n)$ for every positive integer n. Therefore $1 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} TR_A(a_n) \leq TR_A(0) \leq 1$, $1 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} CR_A(a_n) \leq CR_A(0) \leq 1$, $0 \leq UR_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} UR_A(a_n) = 0$ and $0 \leq FR_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} FR_A(a_n) = 0$. Thus we have $TR_A(0) = 1$, $CR_A(0) = 1$, $UR_A(0) = 0$ and $FR_A(0) = 0$. \square

Proposition 3.7.

If every Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra A of R satisfies the conditions (5.3.3)($\forall x, y \in R$)($TR_A(x - y) \geq TR_A(y)$, $CR_A(x - y) \geq CR_A(y)$, $UR_A(x - y) \leq UR_A(y)$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq FR_A(y)$), then TR_A, CR_A, UR_A and FR_A are constant functions.

Proof.

It follows from (5.3.3) that $TR_A(x) = TR_A(x - 0) \geq TR_A(0)$, $CR_A(x) = CR_A(x - 0) \geq CR_A(0)$, $UR_A(x) = UR_A(x - 0) \leq UR_A(0)$ and $FR_A(x) = FR_A(x - 0) \leq FR_A(0)$ for any $x \in R$. By proposition (5.3.2), we have $TR_A(x) = TR_A(0)$, $CR_A(x) = CR_A(0)$, $UR_A(x) = UR_A(0)$ and $FR_A(x) = FR_A(0)$ for any $x \in R$. Hence TR_A, CR_A, UR_A and FR_A are constant functions. \square

Theorem 3.8.

Every subalgebra of R can be represented as an $(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)$ -level set of a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra A of R.

Proof.

Let S be a subalgebra of R and let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. Define a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A in R as follows:

$$TR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} \alpha_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \alpha_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$CR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} \beta_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \beta_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$UR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} \delta_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \delta_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

and

$$FR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} \xi_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \xi_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1]$ and $\delta_1, \xi_1 \in [0, 1]$ with $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2, \beta_1 > \beta_2, \delta_1 < \delta_2, \xi_1 < \xi_2$ and $0 \leq \alpha_1^2 + \beta_1^2 + \delta_1^2 + \xi_1^2 \leq 3, 0 \leq \alpha_2^2 + \beta_2^2 + \delta_2^2 + \xi_2^2 \leq 3$. Obviously, $S = A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \delta_1, \xi_1)}$. We now prove that A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. Let $x, y \in R$. If $x, y \in S$, then $x - y \in S$ because S is a subalgebra of S. Hence $TR_A(x) = TR_A(y) = TR_A(x - y) = \alpha_1, CR_A(x) = CR_A(y) = CR_A(x - y) = \beta_1, UR_A(x) = UR_A(y) = UR_A(x - y) = \delta_1, FR_A(x) = FR_A(y) = FR_A(x - y) = \xi_1$ and so $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\}, CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\}, UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\}$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\}$. Obviously, if $x \notin S$ and $y \notin S$, then $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\} = \alpha_2, CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\} = \beta_2, UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\} = \delta_2$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\} = \xi_2$. Therefore A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. \square

Theorem 3.9.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set of R and let $\alpha, \beta \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \delta^2 + \xi^2 \leq 3$. Define a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A^* in R as follows:

$$TR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} TR_A(x) & \text{if } x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \xi)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$CR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} CR_A(x) & \text{if } x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \xi)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

$$UR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} UR_A(x) & \text{if } x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \xi)} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

and

$$FR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} FR_A(x) & \text{if } x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \xi)} \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

If A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R, then so is A^* .

Proof.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. By theorem 5.3.8, all of $(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)$ -level set $x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ are subalgebras of R. If $x, y \in x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$, then $x - y \in x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ If $x \notin A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ or $y \notin A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$, then $TR_{A^*}(x) = 0, IR_{A^*}(x) = 0, FR_{A^*}(x) = 1$ or $TR_{A^*}(y) = 0, IR_{A^*}(y) = 0, FR_{A^*}(y) = 1$. Therefore we get $TR_{A^*}(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_{A^*}(x), TR_{A^*}(y)\} = 0, CR_{A^*}(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_{A^*}(x), CR_{A^*}(y)\} = 0, UR_{A^*}(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_{A^*}(x), UR_{A^*}(y)\} = 1$ and $FR_{A^*}(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_{A^*}(x), FR_{A^*}(y)\} = 1$ for any $x, y \in R$. Thus A^* is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. \square

Definition 3.10.

A Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A in R is called a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R if it satisfies (5.3.2) and

$$(5.3.4)(\forall x, y \in R)(TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\}, CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(x - y), CR_A(y)\}, UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\} \text{ and } FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\}).$$

Proposition 3.11.

Every Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R.

Proof.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R. Put $x := x - y$ and $y := x$ in (5.3.4). Then we have $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A((x - y) - x), TR_A(x)\}, IR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{IR_A((x - y) - x), IR_A(x)\}$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A((x - y) - x), FR_A(x)\}$. It follows from (5.3.3) and (5.3.2) that

$$TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A((x - x) - y), TR_A(x)\} = \min\{TR_A(0), TR_A(x)\} \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_A(y)\},$$

$$CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A((x - y) - x), CR_A(x)\} = \min\{CR_A(0), CR_A(x)\} \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_A(y)\},$$

$$UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A((x - y) - x), UR_A(x)\} = \max\{UR_A(0), UR_A(x)\} \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_A(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$$FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A((x - y) - x), FR_A(x)\} = \max\{FR_A(0), FR_A(x)\} \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_A(y)\}, \text{ for any } x, y \in R. \text{ Thus A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R.}$$

The converse of Proposition 5.3.11 may not be true in general(see Example 5.3.12.) \square

Example 3.12.

(a) Let $R = \{0,a,b,c\}$ be a subtraction algebra with the following table:

-	0	a	b	C
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	A
b	b	b	0	B
c	c	c	c	0

Define a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set A in R as follows:

$$TR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.72 & \text{if } x \in \{0,a\} \\ 0.11 & \text{if } x \in \{b,c\} \end{cases},$$

$$CR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.72 & \text{if } x \in \{0,a\} \\ 0.11 & \text{if } x \in \{b,c\} \end{cases},$$

$$UR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{0,a\} \\ 0.71 & \text{if } x \in \{b,c\} \end{cases},$$

and

$$FR_A : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{0,a\} \\ 0.71 & \text{if } x \in \{b,c\} \end{cases},$$

It is easy to check that A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R.

(b) Let $R = \{0,1,2,3\}$ be a subtraction algebra as in Example 5.3.3. Define a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set B in R as follows:

$$TR_B : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.33 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0.12 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \\ 0.03 & \text{if } x = 3 \end{cases},$$

$$CR_B : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.33 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0.12 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\} \\ 0.03 & \text{if } x = 3 \end{cases},$$

$$UR_B : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.11 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0.15 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\}, \\ 0.36 & \text{if } x = 3 \end{cases}$$

and

$$FR_B : R \longrightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.11 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 0.15 & \text{if } x \in \{1,2\}. \\ 0.36 & \text{if } x = 3 \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that B is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R. But it is not a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R, since $TR_B(3) = 0.03 \not\geq \min\{TR_B(3 - 1), TR_B(1)\} = \max\{TR_B(2), TR_B(1)\} = 0.12$

Theorem 3.13.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set in R and let $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi \in [0,1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \delta^2 + \xi^2 \leq 3$. Then A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R if and only if all of $(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)$ -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ are ideals of R when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)} \neq \emptyset$.

Proof.

Assume that A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R. Let $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi \in [0,1]$ be such that $0 \leq \alpha^2 + \beta^2 + \delta^2 + \xi^2 \leq 3$ and $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)} \neq \emptyset$. Let $x, y \in R$ be such that $x - y, y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$. Then $TR_A(x - y) \geq \alpha, TR_A(y) \geq \alpha, CR_A(x - y) \geq \beta, CR_A(y) \geq \beta, UR_A(x - y) \leq \delta, UR_A(y) \leq \delta$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \xi, FR_A(y) \leq \xi$. By Definition (5.3.10), we have $TR_A(0) \geq TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\} \geq \alpha, CR_A(0) \geq CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(x - y), CR_A(y)\} \geq \beta, UR_A(0) \leq UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\} \leq \delta$ and $FR_A(0) \leq FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\} \leq \xi$. Hence $0, x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$. Therefore $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi)}$ is an ideal of R.

Conversely, suppose that there exist $a, b, c \in R$ such that $TR_A(0) < TR_A(a), CR_A(0) < CR_A(b), UR_A(0) > UR_A(d)$ and $FR_A(0) > FR_A(e)$. Then there exist, $a_t, b_t \in (0, 1]$ and $c_t, d_t, e_t \in [0, 1)$ such that $TR_A(0) < a_t < TR_A(a), CR_A(0) < b_t < CR_A(b), UR_A(0) > d_t > UR_A(d)$ and $FR_A(0) > e_t > FR_A(e)$. Hence $0 \notin A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t, d_t, e_t)}$, which is a contradiction. Therefore $TR_A(0) \geq TR_A(x), CR_A(0) \geq CR_A(x), UR_A(0) \leq UR_A(x)$ and $FR_A(0) \leq FR_A(x)$ for all $x \in R$. Assume that there exist $a_t, b_t, a_c, b_c, a_g, b_g, a_u, b_u, a_f, b_f \in R$ such that $TR_A(a_t) < \min\{TR_A(a_t - b_t), TR_A(b_t)\}, CR_A(a_c) < \min\{CR_A(a_c - b_c), CR_A(b_c)\}, UR_A(a_u) > \max\{UR_A(a_u - b_u), UR_A(b_u)\}$ and $FR_A(a_f) > \max\{FR_A(a_f - b_f), FR_A(b_f)\}$. Then there exist $s_t, s_c \in (0, 1]$ and $s_g, s_u, s_f \in [0, 1)$ such that $TR_A(a_t) < s_t \leq \min\{TR_A(a_t - b_t), TR_A(b_t)\}, CR_A(a_c) < s_c \leq \min\{CR_A(a_c - b_c), CR_A(b_c)\}, UR_A(a_u) >$

$s_u \geq \max\{UR_A(a_u - b_u), UR_A(b_u)\}$ and $FR_A(a_f) > s_f \geq \max\{FR_A(a_f - b_f), FR_A(b_f)\}$. Hence $a_t - b_t, b_t, a_c - b_c, a_g \in A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t)}$ and $b_t, b_i, b_f \in A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t)}$. But $a_t, a_i \notin A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t)}$ and $a_f \notin A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t)}$. This is a contradiction. Therefore $TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\}$, $CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(x - y), CR_A(y)\}$, $UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\}$ and $FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\}$ for any $x, y \in R$. Therefore A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R. \square

Proposition 3.14.

Every Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal A of R satisfies the following properties:

- (i) $(\forall x, y \in R) (x \leq y \Rightarrow TR_A(x) \geq TR_A(y), CR_A(x) \geq CR_A(y), UR_A(x) \leq UR_A(y), FR_A(x) \leq FR_A(y))$,
- (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in R) (x - y \leq z \Rightarrow TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(y), TR_A(z)\}, CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(y), CR_A(z)\}, UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(y), UR_A(z)\}$ and $FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(y), FR_A(z)\}$).

Proof.

(i) Let $x, y \in R$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $x - y = 0$. Using (1.4) and (1.2), we have $TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\} = \min\{TR_A(0), TR_A(y)\} = TR_A(y)$, $CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(x - y), CR_A(y)\} = \min\{CR_A(0), CR_A(y)\} = CR_A(y)$, $UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\} = \max\{UR_A(0), UR_A(y)\} = UR_A(y)$ and $FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\} = \max\{FR_A(0), FR_A(y)\} = FR_A(y)$.

(ii) Let $x, y, z \in R$ be such that $x - y \leq z$. By (5.3.4) and (5.3.2), we get $TR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{TR_A((x - y) - z), TR_A(z)\} = \min\{TR_A(0), TR_A(z)\} = TR_A(z)$, $CR_A(x - y) \geq \min\{CR_A((x - y) - z), CR_A(z)\} = \min\{CR_A(0), CR_A(z)\} = CR_A(z)$, $UR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{UR_A((x - y) - z), UR_A(z)\} = \max\{UR_A(0), UR_A(z)\} = UR_A(z)$ and $FR_A(x - y) \leq \max\{FR_A((x - y) - z), FR_A(z)\} = \max\{FR_A(0), FR_A(z)\} = FR_A(z)$.

Hence $TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\} \geq \min\{TR_A(y), TR_A(z)\}$, $CR_A(x) \geq \min\{CR_A(x - y), CR_A(y)\} \geq \min\{CR_A(y), CR_A(z)\}$, $UR_A(x) \leq \max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\} \leq \max\{UR_A(y), UR_A(z)\}$ and $FR_A(x) \leq \max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\} \leq \max\{FR_A(y), FR_A(z)\}$, for any $x, y, z \in R$. The following corollary is easily proved by induction. \square

Corollary 3.15.

Every Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal A of R satisfies the following property:

$$(5.3.5) (\forall x, a_1, \dots, a_n \in R)((\dots(x - a_1) - \dots) - a_n = 0 \Rightarrow TR_A(x) \geq \wedge_{k=1}^n TR_A(a_k), CR_A(x) \geq \wedge_{k=1}^n CR_A(a_k), UR_A(x) \leq \vee_{k=1}^n UR_A(a_k), FR_A(x) \leq \vee_{k=1}^n FR_A(a_k)).$$

Definition 3.16.

Let A and B be Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic sets of a set X. The union of A and B is defined to be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set

$$A \cup \sim B := \{ \langle x, TR_{A \cup B}(x), CR_{A \cup B}(x), UR_{A \cup B}(x), FR_{A \cup B}(x) \rangle | x \in R \},$$

where $TR_{A \cup B}(x) = \max\{TR_A(x), TR_B(x)\}$, $CR_{A \cup B}(x) = \max\{CR_A(x), CR_B(x)\}$, $UR_{A \cup B}(x) = \min\{UR_A(x), UR_B(x)\}$ and $FR_{A \cup B}(x) = \min\{FR_A(x), FR_B(x)\}$, for all $x \in R$. The intersection of A and B is defined to be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set

$$A \cap \sim B := \{ \langle x, TR_{A \cap B}(x), CR_{A \cap B}(x), UR_{A \cap B}(x), FR_{A \cap B}(x) \rangle | x \in R \},$$

where $TR_{A \cap B}(x) = \min\{TR_A(x), TR_B(x)\}$, $CR_{A \cap B}(x) = \min\{CR_A(x), CR_B(x)\}$, $UR_{A \cap B}(x) = \max\{UR_A(x), UR_B(x)\}$ and $FR_{A \cap B}(x) = \max\{FR_A(x), FR_B(x)\}$, for all $x \in R$.

Theorem 3.17.

The intersection of two Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideals of R is also a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R.

Proof.

Let A and B be Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideals of R.

For any $x \in R$, we have $TR_{A \cap B}(0) = \min\{TR_A(0), TR_B(0)\} \geq \min\{TR_A(x), TR_B(x)\} = TR_{A \cap B}(x)$, $CR_{A \cap B}(0) = \min\{CR_A(0), CR_B(0)\} \geq \min\{CR_A(x), CR_B(x)\} = CR_{A \cap B}(x)$, $UR_{A \cap B}(0) = \max\{UR_A(0), UR_B(0)\} \leq \max\{UR_A(x), UR_B(x)\} = UR_{A \cap B}(x)$ and $FR_{A \cap B}(0) = \max\{FR_A(0), FR_B(0)\} \leq \max\{FR_A(x), FR_B(x)\} = FR_{A \cap B}(x)$. Let $x, y \in R$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} TR_{A \cap B}(x) &= \min\{TR_A(x), TR_B(x)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{TR_A(x-y), TR_A(y)\}, \min\{TR_B(x-y), TR_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{TR_A(x-y), TR_B(x-y)\}, \min\{TR_A(y), TR_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{TR_{A \cap B}(x-y), TR_{A \cap B}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} CR_{A \cap B}(x) &= \min\{CR_A(x), CR_B(x)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{CR_A(x-y), CR_A(y)\}, \min\{CR_B(x-y), CR_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{CR_A(x-y), CR_B(x-y)\}, \min\{CR_A(y), CR_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{CR_{A \cap B}(x-y), CR_{A \cap B}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 UR_{A \cap B}(x) &= \max\{UR_A(x), UR_B(x)\} \\
 &\leq \max\{\max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_A(y)\}, \max\{UR_B(x - y), UR_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{\max\{UR_A(x - y), UR_B(x - y)\}, \max\{UR_A(y), UR_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{UR_{A \cap B}(x - y), UR_{A \cap B}(y)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 FR_{A \cap B}(x) &= \max\{FR_A(x), FR_B(x)\} \\
 &\leq \max\{\max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_A(y)\}, \max\{FR_B(x - y), FR_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{\max\{FR_A(x - y), FR_B(x - y)\}, \max\{FR_A(y), FR_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{FR_{A \cap B}(x - y), FR_{A \cap B}(y)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $A \cap \sim B$ is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R . \square

Corollary 3.18.

If $\{A_i | i \in N\}$ is a family of Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideals of R , then so is $\bigcap_{i \in N} \sim A_i$.

Proposition 3.19.

Let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic ideal of R . Then $R_{TR} := \{x \in R | TR_A(x) = TR_A(0)\}$, $R_{CR} := \{x \in R | CR_A(x) = CR_A(0)\}$, $R_{UR} := \{x \in R | UR_A(x) = UR_A(0)\}$ and $R_{FR} := \{x \in R | FR_A(x) = FR_A(0)\}$ are ideals of R .

Proof.

Clearly, $0 \in R_{TR}$. Let $x - y, y \in R_{TR}$. Then $TR_A(x - y) = TR_A(0)$ and $TR_A(y) = TR_A(0)$. It follows from (1.4) that $TR_A(x) \geq \min\{TR_A(x - y), TR_A(y)\} = TR_A(0)$. By (1.2), we get $TR_A(x) = TR_A(0)$. Hence $x \in R_{TR}$. Therefore R_{TR} is an ideal of R . By a similar way, R_{CR}, R_{UR} and R_{FR} are ideals of R . Let $F: R \rightarrow S$ be a function of sets. If

$$M = \{\langle y, TR_M(y), CR_M(y), UR_M(y), FR_M(y) \rangle | y \in S\}$$

is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set of a set S , then the preimage of M under f is defined to be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^{-1}(M) &= \{\langle x, f^{-1}(TR_M)(x), f^{-1}(CR_M)(x), f^{-1}(UR_M)(x), f^{-1}(FR_M)(x) \rangle | x \in R\} \\
 &\text{of } R, \text{ where } f^{-1}(TR_M)(x) = TR_M(f(x)), f^{-1}(CR_M)(x) = CR_M(f(x)), f^{-1}(UR_M)(x) = UR_M(f(x)) \\
 &\text{and } f^{-1}(FR_M)(x) = FR_M(f(x)) \text{ for all } x \in R. \square
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.20.

Let $f : R \rightarrow S$ be a homomorphism of subtraction algebras. If $M = \{\langle y, TR_M(y), CR_M(y), UR_M(y), FR_M(y) \rangle | y \in S\}$ is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of S ,

then the preimage of M under f is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R.

Proof.

Let $f^{-1}(M)$ be the preimage of M under f. For any $x, y \in R$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(TR_M(x - y)) &= TR_M(f(x - y)) = TR_M(f(x) - f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{TR_M(f(x)), TR_M(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{f^{-1}(TR_M)(x), f^{-1}(TR_M)(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(CR_M(x - y)) &= CR_M(f(x - y)) = CR_M(f(x) - f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{CR_M(f(x)), CR_M(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{f^{-1}(CR_M)(x), f^{-1}(CR_M)(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(UR_M(x - y)) &= UR_M(f(x - y)) = UR_M(f(x) - f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{UR_M(f(x)), UR_M(f(y))\} \\ &= \max\{f^{-1}(UR_M)(x), f^{-1}(UR_M)(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f^{-1}(FR_M(x - y)) &= FR_M(f(x - y)) = FR_M(f(x) - f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{FR_M(f(x)), FR_M(f(y))\} \\ &= \max\{f^{-1}(FR_M)(x), f^{-1}(FR_M)(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(M)$ is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R.

Let $f : R \rightarrow S$ be an onto function of sets. If A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set

$$f(A) := \{\langle y, f(TR_A)(y), f(CR_A)(y), f(UR_A)(y), f(FR_A)(y) \rangle | y \in S\}$$

of S, where $f(TR_A)(y) = \vee_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} TR_A(x)$, $f(CR_A)(y) = \vee_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} CR_A(x)$, $f(UR_A)(y) = \wedge_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} UR_A(x)$ and $f(FR_A)(y) = \wedge_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} FR_A(x)$. \square

Theorem 3.21.

For an onto homomorphism $f : R \rightarrow S$ of subtraction algebras, let A be a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic set of R such that

$$(1.6)(\forall C \subseteq R) (\exists x_0 \in C) (TR_A(x_0) = \vee_{z \in C} TR_A(z), CR_A(x_0) = \vee_{z \in C} CR_A(z), UR_A(x_0) = \wedge_{z \in C} UR_A(z), FR_A(x_0) = \wedge_{z \in C} FR_A(z)).$$

If A is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of R, then the image of A under f is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of S.

Proof.

Let $f(A)$ be the image of A under f . Let $a, b \in S$. Then $f^{-1}(a) \neq \emptyset$ and $f^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset$ in R . By (5.3.6), there exist $x_a \in f^{-1}(a)$ and $x_b \in f^{-1}(b)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} TR_A(x_a) &= \bigvee_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} TR_A(z), CR_A(x_a) = \bigvee_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} CR_A(z), \\ UR_A(x_a) &= \bigwedge_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} UR_A(z), FR_A(x_a) = \bigwedge_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} FR_A(z), \\ TR_A(x_b) &= \bigvee_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} TR_A(w), CR_A(x_b) = \bigvee_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} CR_A(w), \\ UR_A(x_b) &= \bigwedge_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} UR_A(w), FR_A(x_b) = \bigwedge_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} FR_A(w), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(TR_A)(a - b) &= \bigvee_{x \in f^{-1}(a-b)} TR_A(x) \geq TR_A(x_a - x_b) \geq \min\{TR_A(x_a), TR_A(x_b)\} \\ &= \min\{\bigvee_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} TR_A(z), \bigvee_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} TR_A(w)\} \\ &= \min\{f(TR_A)(a), f(TR_A)(b)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(CR_A)(a - b) &= \bigvee_{x \in f^{-1}(a-b)} CR_A(x) \geq CR_A(x_a - x_b) \geq \min\{CR_A(x_a), CR_A(x_b)\} \\ &= \min\{\bigvee_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} CR_A(z), \bigvee_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} CR_A(w)\} \\ &= \min\{f(CR_A)(a), f(CR_A)(b)\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} f(UR_A)(a - b) &= \bigwedge_{x \in f^{-1}(a-b)} UR_A(x) \leq UR_A(x_a - x_b) \leq \max\{UR_A(x_a), UR_A(x_b)\} \\ &= \max\{\bigwedge_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} UR_A(z), \bigwedge_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} UR_A(w)\} \\ &= \max\{f(UR_A)(a), f(UR_A)(b)\}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f(FR_A)(a - b) &= \bigwedge_{x \in f^{-1}(a-b)} FR_A(x) \leq FR_A(x_a - x_b) \leq \max\{FR_A(x_a), FR_A(x_b)\} \\ &= \max\{\bigwedge_{z \in f^{-1}(a)} FR_A(z), \bigwedge_{w \in f^{-1}(b)} FR_A(w)\} \\ &= \max\{f(FR_A)(a), f(FR_A)(b)\}, \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(A)$ is a Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic subalgebra of S . \square

References

- [1] Ahn. S. S and Kim. Y. H., Quotient subtraction algebras by an int-soft ideal, Journal of Computational Analysis and Applications, 25 (2018), 728 - 737.
- [2] Atanassov. K., Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 20 (1986).
- [3] Chul Hwan Park., Neutrosophic ideal of Subtraction Algebras, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 24 (2019), 36 - 45.
- [4] Jun. Y. B, Kim. H. S and Roh. E. H., Ideal theory of subtraction algebras, Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae (online), (2004), 397 - 402.
- [5] Jun. Y. B, Kim. Y. H and Oh. K. A., Subtraction algebras with additional conditions, Communications of the Korean Mathematical Society, 22 (2007), 1 - 7.
- [6] Ramya. M., Murali. S., Radha. R., Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Sets, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, 10(9) (2022), 36 - 42.
- [7] Schein. B. M., Difference Semigroups, Communications in Algebra, 20 (1992), 2153 - 2169.

Ramya M, Murali S, Radha R, Princy R, Fermatean Quadripartitioned Neutrosophic Ideals in Subtraction Algebra

-
- [8] Smarandache. F., Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic probability, set and logic, Amer Res Press, Rehoboth, USA, (1998), 105.
- [9] Zadeh. L. A, Fuzzy Sets, Information and Control, 8(1965) 338 - 353.
- [10] Zelinka. B., Subtraction Semigroups, Mathematica Bohemica, 120 (1995), 445 - 447.

Received: April 16, 2025. Accepted: Sep 20, 2025